

Statistical test for cyclostationarity based on CSC-based indicators - application to vibration signals from electric motor

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September, 11, 2024

Co-funded by
the European Union

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP

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of Science and Technology

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Introduction (1/2)

- We introduce a methodology for testing second-order signals with cyclostationary behavior
- The proposed indicators based on the Cyclic Spectral Coherence (CSC) map are considered here as test statistics
- Procedure is designed to distinguish between healthy machinery signals and those indicating local damage
- Monte Carlo simulations employed to compute distributions of the test statistics and acceptance regions
- Method is validated using simulated signals with different Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) levels
- Practical application is demonstrated on vibration signals from an electric motor.

Introduction (2/2)

Cyclic modulation of the signal is demonstrated by a set of harmonics in the envelope spectrum. The presence of more harmonic components with higher amplitudes indicates stronger modulation and more accurate detection.

In the case of damage, the value of the energy corresponding to the frequency of the damage and its harmonics is higher than that of the signal coming from a healthy machine (without damage).

Problem formulation

- The goal is to assign a signal into “good” or “bad” class based on parameterization of CSC map, taking into consideration statistical significance of statistical testing procedure.
- The main difficulty is to define a parameter that will allow to robustly conduct such classification. Therefore, it is proposed to use CSC map as a working data representation, since cyclostationary analysis is one of the best approaches to conducting local damage detection investigations.
- Past attempts included analyzing entire matrices of CSC maps, or aggregating them to EES vector for classification. This time authors try to classify the data based on a single parameter.

Methodology

Cyclic Spectral Coherence map

The classical tool used to identify the cyclostationary behaviour of a given time series $\{X_t\}$ is the cyclic spectral coherence. It is a double Fourier transform of the instantaneous autocovariance function:

$$C_X(f, \epsilon) = \frac{S_X(f, \epsilon)}{\sqrt{S_X\left(f + \frac{\epsilon}{2}, 0\right) S_X\left(f - \frac{\epsilon}{2}, 0\right)}}$$

where

$$S_X(f, \epsilon) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=-N}^N \sum_{\tau=-\infty}^{\infty} R_X(t, \tau) e^{-i2\pi f\tau} e^{-i2\pi\epsilon t}$$

CSC-based indicators

Let $\epsilon_l = \{\epsilon_{l_1}, \epsilon_{l_2}, \dots, \epsilon_{l_p}\}$ be the modulating frequency for the periodic component corresponding to the fault (frequency of the fault and its harmonics).

The sum and maximum of the energy of the fault component are proposed as the first two test statistics

$$\hat{I}S^1 = \sum_{\epsilon_l \in \mathcal{E}} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \hat{C}_X(f, \epsilon)$$

$$\hat{I}S^2 = \max_{\epsilon_l \in \mathcal{E}, f \in \mathcal{F}} \hat{C}_X(f, \epsilon)$$

The third considered statistic, compares the total energy of these components with the total energy of the enhanced envelope spectrum (EES) within the specified frequency range

$$\hat{I}S^3 = \frac{\hat{I}S^1}{\sum_{\epsilon \in \mathcal{E}} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \hat{C}_X(f, \epsilon)}$$

Testing procedure

Based on the proposed statistics the following null (H_0) and alternative (H_1) hypotheses are considered:

H_0 : given signal does not exhibit cyclostationary behavior

H_1 : given signal exhibits cyclostationary behavior.

In the context of local damage detection considered in this paper, the defined above hypotheses correspond to the following cases:

H_0 : given signal corresponds to the healthy machine

H_1 : given signal corresponds to the machine with local damage

Testing procedure

Learning stage

- Import M signals from healthy machine
- Calculate the CSC map for each signal
- Calculate the values of test statistics $\hat{I}\hat{S}$ for each signal
- Calculate the acceptance region based on the empirical quantiles of the test statistics obtained from the healthy machine

Testing stage

- Import signal
- Calculate CSC map
- Calculate the value of test statistic
- Verify if the test statistic fall into the acceptance region
- Decision making

Model of the signal

The following model of the signal is considered:

$$X_t = s(t) + \sigma Z_t$$

=

+

**Considered signal
(additive model)**

**Deterministic component
Signal of interest (SOI)**

**Independent identically
distributed (i.i.d.) Gaussian
random variables
NOISE $N(0,1)$**

Simulation

Simulation

Estimated PDFs of the test statistics for signals corresponding to two healthy (different variance) and two unhealthy cases (SNR 0.13 and 3.99).

Acceptance regions for three test statistics (under null hypotheses) and the boxplots of the test statistics corresponding to the considered unhealthy cases.

The distributions of all test statistics in healthy cases exhibit significant overlap independent of variance (similar PDFs,). The larger the SNR, the farther the statistical distributions are from the PDF of the healthy data.

Simulation

ZOOM

Statistical test power for different SNR levels we individually compute the power for each test using $M=100$ simulated signals derived from model. The test's power is derived as the average number of rejections of the hypothesis H_0 for signals associated with the hypothesis H_1 .

For the SNR values exceeding **0.2**, the test powers are equal to 1 for all examined statistics.

Object description (1/2)

The configuration of the experimental setup.

Object description (2/2)

Case 1: Healthy bearing

Outer race faults

Case 2: Bearing with damaged outer race (small damage)

Case 3: Bearing with damaged outer race (large damage)

Characteristic frequencies of the bearing	
Rotational speed	1498 rpm
Shaft	24.967 Hz
Rolling element set & cage	9.945 Hz
Rolling element about its axis	58.856 Hz
Inner ring	135.194 Hz
Outer ring	89.506 Hz
Rolling element	117.712 Hz

Data description

Case 1: Healthy bearing

Case 2: Bearing with damaged outer race (small damage)

Case 3: Bearing with damaged outer race (large damage)

Changes in the amplitudes in the time series and frequency structure in the spectrograms between the healthy signal and the damaged signals can be observed.

Results

Case 1: Healthy bearing

The cyclic components identified on the map do not necessarily indicate damage (e.g., 25 Hz corresponding to the rotation of the shaft). This behaviour was not observed for the simulated signals.

Case 2: Bearing with damaged outer race (small damage)

Case 3: Bearing with damaged outer race (large damage)

In the remaining two cases, the component associated with the frequency of damage is distinctly evident. Furthermore, when the damage is significant (Case 3) these components are observable across the entire carrier frequency band.

Results

Estimated PDFs of the test statistics for signals corresponding to healthy Case 1 and two unhealthy cases: Case 2 and Case 3.

Acceptance regions for three test statistics (under null hypotheses) and the boxplots of the test statistics corresponding to the considered unhealthy cases.

The substantial difference of the distributions of the three considered statistics for healthy and unhealthy cases was significant enough for the tests to reject the null hypothesis.

Summary

1. The proposed approach uses the Cyclic Spectral Coherence bi-frequency map and proposes simple indicators derived from this map as test statistics in a hypothesis testing procedure.
2. The efficiency of proposed methodology is validated through Monte Carlo simulations on generated signals with varying Signal-to-Noise Ratio levels, demonstrating its effectiveness in detecting local damage even at low SNR values.
3. The method is also applied to vibration data from healthy and faulty (damaged outer ring) bearings installed in an electric motor.

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